

THE NEED TO DEVELOP THE TEACHER'S SPIRITUAL IMAGE.

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Abstract: This article examines the issues of developing the teacher's spiritual image. In addition, the important components of the development of the spiritual image of the teacher are covered in detail.

In the conditions of the new Uzbekistan, the reforms implemented in the socio-economic and spiritual spheres are also related to the improvement of the professional skill level of pedagogical staff, and the task of developing the spiritual image of teachers is clearly visible as a priority direction. After all, only the development of the young generation and the development of the moral image of the teachers depends on the development of the moral character of the young generation.

How urgent this issue is The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoev, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan on December 20, 2022, stated that "Increasing the quality of education is the only and only right way to the development of New Uzbekistan." In his lectures, our head of state noted that "Salvation is in education, salvation in upbringing, salvation in knowledge" because all good goals are achieved through education and training.

the Honorable President defined a number of important tasks to improve the efficiency of the educational process and organize the educational process. Including

- raising the quality of education in schools;
- increasing the prestige of the teaching profession in society;
- improving the conditions of teachers;
- increase the status of teachers, their honor and dignity;
- formation of students' free and creative thinking, teamwork and communication skills (21st century skills, i.e., 4 K skills);
- use of advanced foreign educational programs ("A-level" is used in Presidential schools);
- organization of separate scientific institutes and laboratories for introduction of advanced educational standards and methods;
- bring highly qualified foreign teachers;

He noted that the responsibility of school teams and teachers in the new Uzbekistan is clearly manifested in these issues [1].

The tasks set by the head of state to increase the efficiency of the educational process and organize the educational process place great responsibility on teachers and coaches.

The reforms carried out in the field of education, the improvement of the quality of educational work, the successful performance of the assigned tasks, first of all, show the

continuous development of the professional activity of pedagogues, that is, the need to further improve the system of developing the moral image of Uzbekistan's pedagogues.

the requirements for the educational process in the 21st century and the readiness of the teacher for these requirements is reflected in his spiritual image.

When thinking about the development of the teacher's spiritual image, first of all, it is appropriate to clarify the meaning of the main concepts such as "spirituality", "spiritual image", "image" related to the problem.

Spirituality is an internal positive, spiritual factor that determines the strength, development, opportunities and prospects of an individual, nation, state and society. Spirituality (Arabic "spirituality" - a set of meanings) is essentially a set of philosophical, legal, scientific, artistic, moral, religious ideas, concepts and ideas that have a positive impact on social development .

The concept of spirituality is complex and varied in its essence and meaning. Spirituality is considered a divine light in the human heart, which is not found in any creature. Spirituality is a magic spell that cannot be completely solved. E. Yusupov, one of the scientists who carried out research in this field, says that "Spirituality is a common system of human morals and manners, knowledge, talent, ability, practical skills, conscience, faith, belief, worldview, ideological views, which positively affects the development of society. system ¹," he describes.

it is defined as "Spirituality is a concept embodying the inner life, spiritual experiences, mental abilities, and perception of society, nation and individual."²

describes spirituality as "divine light, symbol of human essence" , I. Saifnazarov refers to the inner meaning of spirituality³

paid more attention ⁴. A. Mukhtorov's comments on the concept of "Spirituality" are also noteworthy. According to him, "Spirituality " is a wide-ranging social phenomenon that expresses ⁵a person's mind, thinking, worldview, trust and belief, opportunity, talent, activity and ability . G. J. Tulenova said, "Spirituality is an important element of any society. There is no society or state without high spirituality and ideology cannot progress either. He expressed the opinion that only a nation with a highly developed spirituality will consistently step towards the future .⁶

It is clear from the above analysis that today spiritual issues are characterized as an important pedagogical problem.

Image in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language (Arabic - appearance, face, aft, height, behavior) is shown to mean. In addition, it is stated that it represents a set of spiritual, mental and moral characteristics of a person, consciousness, worldview, level of knowledge and so on [3]. Regarding the profession and people, the spiritual image of a certain person - what they do determines their image. It can be seen from this that the spiritual image

¹ Yusupov E. Spiritual foundations of human development. - T.: University, 1998. - B.34.

² Ibrohimov A., Sultanov H., Joraev N. A sense of homeland. - T.: Uzbekistan, 1997.

³ Karshiboev M. From chaos to harmony. - T.: Spirituality, 1997. - P.7-12.

⁴ Saifnazarov I. Spiritual perfection and political culture _ – T. _ : Shark, 2001. – B. 14.

⁵ Mukhtorov A. Raising a healthy generation with high spirituality is our goal // Independent Uzbekistan: current problems of philosophical sciences (brief texts of lectures). - T., 2000. - Collection. UzRFA –B. 105-108.

⁶ Tulenova G.J. The need for development to improve the spirituality and maturity of young people (current problems of the philosophical sciences of independent Uzbekistan) //(Summary of lectures). - T., 2000. - Collection. RFA. - B.103.

of the teacher must be reflected in his activity, behavior, behavior, thoughts and practical aspects.

Of course, many aspects of spirituality and image are expressed in all the definitions given above. Although the authors express their views, these definitions need further refinement. Based on the above conclusions, we tried to define the spiritual image as follows.

In our opinion, when we **say the spiritual image of a teacher**, it is appropriate to understand the image of a pedagogue who embodies high enlightenment, who is an example to all, who embodies inner and outer beauty, and who is advanced in professional skills.

In addition, it is appropriate to recognize the following aspects as important components of the teacher's spiritual image:

- high enlightenment (in-depth knowledge of one's field and related fields),
- high spirituality (high behavior, possession of inner (internal) and external (external) beauty),
- stable mentality (always mentally stable and calm in activity),
- high professional (pedagogical) skills, including pedagogical manners, pedagogical skills, pedagogical communication culture, pedagogical relaxation, ability to exert communicative influence, pedagogical tact, pedagogical technique, speech technique, pedagogical creativity, pedagogical experience, pedagogical culture, competence (ability) and communicative (ability to communicate and exchange information), collaborative (cooperation and teamwork), creativity (creativity, creativity), critical thinking (critical and logical thinking (4K-skills),
- leadership and management thorough mastery of skills (leadership in activity, following, being an example, an example, being able to set an example),
- legal criteria to know and in practice application (knowing one's rights, understanding one's dignity and worth, fulfilling one's obligations and duties),
- historical thinking (respect for the heritage of ancestors, pride and use of them, loyalty to our national values),
- the level of development of ideological training (noble thoughts, creative ideas, positive thinking, scientific outlook) should be demonstrated (Table 1).

For this, it is important to further develop a new worldview, high spirituality, patriotism, dedication, stable mental and moral characteristics, consciousness, and thinking in pedagogues.

In this process, they are required to continuously develop themselves, willpower, responsibility, dedication to their profession, fulfillment of professional needs and development of professional skills.

Table 1.

Important components of the teacher's spiritual image.

T.r	Components	Content	
1	High enlightenment	In-depth knowledge of his field and related fields	
2	High spirituality	High character, inner (inner) and outer (outer) beauty	

3	Stable mentality (psychological)	Always mentally stable and restrained in activity	
4	High professional (pedagogical) skills	1. Pedagogical manners, pedagogical ability, pedagogical communication culture, pedagogical relaxation, ability to exert communicative influence, pedagogical tact, pedagogical technique, speech technique, pedagogical creativity, pedagogical experience, pedagogical culture, competence (ability) ; 2. Acquisition of aspects such as communication (ability to communicate and exchange information), collaboration (cooperation and team work), creativity (creativity, creativity), critical thinking (critical and logical thinking (4K-24th century skills)	
5	Leadership and management thorough mastery of skills	able to lead, follow, set an example, set an example	
6	Legal criteria to know and in practice apply	To know one's rights, to realize one's dignity and worth, to fulfill one's obligations and duties	
7	Development of historical thinking	Respect for the heritage of ancestors, pride and use of them, loyalty to our national values	
8	Ideological training	Noble thoughts, creative ideas, creative thinking, scientific outlook	

In conclusion, it can be said that the development of society cannot be imagined without the effective work of teachers. Therefore, it is necessary for all our pedagogues to deeply understand that the issue of developing the traditional image of teachers, which is an important factor in the development of New Uzbekistan, is the demand of the times, and to develop our own spiritual image in this way. Because the future of young people is in the hands of teachers-coaches.

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